

Virtual Imaging Trials in Medicine
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PROCEEDINGS

1048-VIT for MVP the role of virtual imaging in healthcare startup ecosystem

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Academic research in applied sciences is a cornerstone of innovative scientific discovery, yet commercialization in healthcare remains challenging due to heavy regulatory pathways, lengthy testing through clinical trials, significant R&D and market penetration costs. This significantly hampers the creation and survival of new health-tech providers (startups), ultimately denying potential benefits for patients. Funding for clinical translation is often a “chicken and egg” type of situation. From one side, venture capital firms (investors) seek investment de-risking activities, such as development of a minimal viable product (MVP) tested in clinical settings with a defined regulatory path. On the other side, MVP development, particularly for AI-based healthcare solutions, relies heavily on medical data access, which is often restricted, outdated, or over-processed.

Virtual imaging platforms, such as the one developed at the Center for Virtual Imaging Trials at Duke University, USA, were primarily designed for the task of optimization and clinical testing of new medical imaging technology. Fast and cheap data generation with access to ground truth makes them also valuable for commercial AI development and validation.

A case study of an early-stage startup developing an AI-based medical imaging software showed that using the DukeSim platform, data generation costs were reduced by 90% compared to acquiring hospital-provided data. Virtual imaging costs are mostly related to the costs of GPU-accelerated computing on cloud-based platforms, while the costs of a traditional approach are related to the administrative and legal fees required to design a compliant data transfer. Generating a correct virtual CT scan in-house took 22 days, with subsequent scans completed in hours, compared to 11 months for clinical data acquisition.

While diversity of anthropomorphic patients limits the full application of AI algorithms in clinical settings, hybrid approaches combining clinical and simulated data and further development of imaging simulators are expected to bridge this gap.
